

Secure Interactive Environments for SensiTiVe data Analytics (SIESTA)

Call: Enabling an operational, open and FAIR EOSC ecosystem – HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01

Topic: Trusted environments for sensitive data management in EOSC – HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-06

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Scope

The SIESTA project aims to deliver trusted cloud-based environments within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) for managing and sharing sensitive data. The project focuses on enhancing the EOSC Exchange services, demonstrating the feasibility of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, and providing tools for secure data anonymization. This policy brief highlights the relevance and contributions of the SIESTA project to various policy areas related to research infrastructures in Europe.

The SIESTA overall goal is to deliver trusted cloud-based environments, in the context of the EOSC, for the management and sharing of sensitive data that are built in a reproducible way, together with a set of services and tools to ease the secure sharing of sensitive data in the EOSC, through state-of-the-art anonymization techniques.

This global objective will be set up through the following five specific objectives:

- O1: Enhance the EOSC Exchange services by delivering a set of cloud-based trusted environments for the analysis of sensitive data in the EOSC demonstrating the feasibility of the FAIR principles over them.
- O2: Study, explore and demonstrate the feasibility of FAIR management and processing of sensitive data, showcasing the benefits for society, science and research.
- O3: Deliver tools for the secure anonymization or pseudonymisation of datasets, allowing rightholders to safely release sensitive data through the EOSC Exchange.
- O4: Provide rightholders and other relevant stakeholders with best practices and methodologies for the release of sensitive data following FAIR principles, including design principles for compute infrastructures allowing access to them, exploring the feasibility of FAIR data workflows over sensitive data.
- O5: Extend the service offer and the capabilities being offered through the EOSC portal, coordinating with the operational and management activities carried out by the EOSC partnership and related projects.

Policy Implications and recommendations

The following are the main relevant contributions of the SIESTA project to the research infrastructure policies in Europe at this stage.

Implementation of Research Infrastructures

The SIESTA project contributes to the implementation of research infrastructures by demonstrating the feasibility of FAIR principles over sensitive data. This is detailed in deliverable D5.1 [1], showcasing how these principles can be effectively applied to sensitive data.

- **Key Results:** Demonstration of FAIR principles over sensitive data, as reported in the SIESTA Report on the tension between FAIR guiding principles and sensitive data.
- **Impact:** Enhanced ability to manage and share sensitive data while adhering to FAIR principles, thereby improving data accessibility and usability.
- **Recommendations:** Increased EU support for the integration and standardization of FAIR principles across research infrastructures.

Technology Development, Data and Digital Services, Digitalisation

The SIESTA project significantly impacts research infrastructures by providing advanced tools for data anonymization, such as pyCANON [2] and Anjana [3], together with tools for reliable publication of data, including risk control measures. These tools can be directly applied to ensure a certain level of anonymization is achieved for datasets, enhancing data security and privacy with regard to the management of sensitive data.

- **Key Results:** Development and application of anonymization tools [4].
- **Impact:** Enhanced data security and privacy through effective anonymization techniques, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations.
- **Recommendations:** Continue investing in technology development and digitalization to drive innovation in data anonymization and security.

Technology development, data and digital services, digitalisation

SIESTA will deliver a set of trusted data labs in the context of the EOSC, aligned with sister projects in the INFRAEOSC ecosystem, demonstrating the feasibility of the application of the FAIR data principles over sensitive data. Via the SIESTA reproducible and secure platform, data rightholders can provide access to sensitive data, via machine-actionable tools, to specific researchers in a trustworthy way.

- **Key Results:** A reproducible and secure cloud environment to analyze sensitive data in the cloud.
- **Impact:** Facilitation of secure and controlled access to sensitive data, promoting trust and collaboration among researchers.
- **Recommendations:** Foster the adoption of these trusted environments across various research domains to maximize their impact and utility.

Employment and skills in research infrastructures

Beyond sensitive data management and processing, where the need for managing ethics and legal issues are normally tackled, the SIESTA consortium members recommend that ethical and legal skills should be included and promoted in the evolving open science skillset at a broader level. Data-driven science poses significant challenges from this perspective, and the EOSC has a good opportunity to support stakeholders (scientists, technicians, managers, etc.) who need to gain knowledge in these areas. Including these aspects (e.g., AI ethical concerns, GDPR, etc.) in the training curricula can increase the research infrastructures personnel skillset.

- **Key Results:** Set of training units including ethical, legal, and managerial aspects, tailored to data users and rightholders.
- **Impact:** Enhanced competency among research personnel in handling ethical and legal issues related to data management, fostering a culture of responsible data use.
- **Recommendations:** Integrate ethical and legal training into standard curricula for research personnel to ensure comprehensive skill development.

Additional Recommendations

Sovereignty of EU Projects in terms of research outputs

EU projects should remain sovereign with regard to widespread tools controlled by commercial companies with their own interests and roadmaps. This includes, but is not limited to, popular software repositories, container or artificial intelligence registries. Without neglecting collaboration and social aspects of these platforms, ensuring EU sovereignty will help maintain control over critical infrastructure and data management practices.

Promote Standards and Best Practices

There is a need for international standards and best practices to ensure interoperability between trusted environments with a specific focus on sensitive data management. Developing and adopting standards or ensuring interoperability via specific crosswalks will facilitate seamless cooperation and data sharing across borders, enhancing the overall impact of research infrastructures.

Future directions

The SIESTA project aims to expand its catalog of services and further integrate its tools and methodologies into the broader EOSC ecosystem. Future efforts will focus on enhancing interoperability with ongoing INFRAEOSC actions, developing additional training programs for ethical and legal skills, and exploring new technologies for data anonymization and security. By continuing to foster collaboration and innovation, SIESTA seeks to make a lasting impact on the management and sharing of sensitive data in Europe and beyond.

References

- [1] J. de la Cueva *et al.*, "D5.1 - Report on the tension between FAIR guiding principles and sensitive data," Jun. 2025, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.15533033.
- [2] J. Sáinz-Pardo Díaz and Á. López García, "A Python library to check the level of anonymity of a dataset," *Sci. Data*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 785, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41597-022-01894-2.
- [3] J. Sáinz-Pardo Díaz and Á. López García, "An Open Source Python Library for Anonymizing Sensitive Data," *Sci. Data*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 1289, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.1038/s41597-024-04019-z.
- [4] J. Sáinz-Pardo Díaz and D. Rodríguez Gonzalez, "D10.1 - SIESTA anonymisation tools," Jun. 2025, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.15533079.

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